

Utilizing the SETR Process in the Procurement of TPSs on the CASS Family of Testers.

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Abstract:

The acquisition of Operational Test Program Sets (OTPSs) has been a recurring effort requiring standardization, refinement, and continuous process improvement. Established in 1989, by the 'Red Team' integrated product team (IPT) and updated in 2005 as the NAVAIR Generic OTPS Request for Proposal (NGOR), the NGOR acquisition package is used as a Government template in the procurement of OTPSs being obtained for the Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) Family of Testers (FoT). This acquisition package has been through several minor and major changes since inception. It has included review and recommendations from all Department of Defense services to include the U.S. Air Force, U.S. Army, U.S. Marines, and U.S. Navy. These services and commercial industry use the NGOR as a reference and guidance for future bids and proposals. Foreign entities have also attributed ideas to include approved Foreign Military Sales (FMS). In 2014, the NGOR was revamped to include the NAVAIR Systems Engineering Technical Review (SETR) process. The rigorous and defined process assesses the technical, logistical, and programmatic health of design and development of an OTPS procurement. This paper will further enhance the understanding of this process by assessing the role and value the NAVAIR SETR process has in the acquisition, development, and over all life cycle management of Test Program Sets (TPSs) for the CASS FoT. This assessment will include the total acquisition life cycle from the Analysis of Alternatives (AoA) to the Materiel Support Date (MSD). Additionally, this paper will identify the changes made to the NGOR to incorporate SETR relative to the Statement of Work (SOW), Performance Specification, Contract Attachments, and Contract Data Requirements Lists (CDRLs). This assessment comprises a discussion on OTPS and TPS system performance specification requirements (both generic and specific), SETR milestone and technical events' entry criteria, SETR checklist prerequisites specific to planned contract events, logistical needs, and federal regulatory and statutory requirements.

Key words – SETR, Systems Engineering, Test Program Sets, Statement of Work, Request for Proposal

I. INTRODUCTION

OTPSs acquisition has been an on-going exercise which has been refined to standardize TPS procurement requirements, deliverables, and procedures; minimize solicitation requirements that provide no value added; simplify Request for Proposal (RFP) preparation; reduce procurement risks; and incorporate lessons learned. For the US Navy, this has resulted in the development of the NAVAIR Generic OTPS RFP (NGOR). The NGOR acquisition package is used as a starting point in the procurement of OTPSs being obtained for the Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) Family of Testers (FoT). Similar to a weapon system, the CASS FoT has configuration control, architecture, and functional requirements for the software and hardware operating on it. OTPSs must therefore be procured and developed in accordance with standards established by the DOD and NAVAIR which are summarized within the NGOR acquisition package.

Over the years, programs have gone awry, being driven over cost, over schedule, or failing to meet performance requirements defined within the contract. This may have been a result of many different factors including; insufficient data and data rights, changing requirements, undefined or unrealistic requirements, or progressing into a design phase without having reached the necessary design maturity. As a result, Naval Air (NAVAIR) implemented the Systems Engineering Technical Review (SETR) Process. NAVAIR Instruction 4355.19 applies SETR events designed to enable an independent assessment of the emerging design against the overall objective of promoting a well-managed development effort leading to a system that meets programmatic requirements while providing the system performance required supporting mission needs^[6]. It is an iterative process that maps the technical reviews to the acquisition process described in DoD 5000 documentation and follows the process described in SETR Process Handbook. The SETR process has been adapted for use within the acquisition community involved with procurement of CASS FoT OTPSs. The SETR process provides a framework for structured systems engineering management in Navy procurements. SETRs also provide program management with independent subject matter assessments of program technical maturity at key milestones in the development life cycle. Each SETR assessment is

focused on verifying technical health and maturity by examining objective products representing program work accomplished to date. The SETR process is event-driven, conducted when the system is ready for review and chaired by technical authorities independent of the program.

II. NAVAIR GENERIC OTPS RFP (NGOR)

In 1989, NAVAIR PMA260 formed the 'Red Team' as a service to Support Equipment Team Leaders (SETLs) and PMAs with a number of goals in mind:

- To standardize OTPS program requirements, deliverables, and procedures
- Eliminate non-value added solicitation requirements
- Simplify Request for Proposal generation
- Reduce cost and schedule associated with proposal preparation
- Better support the acquisition effort associated with procuring OTPSs
- Support field activities involved with OTPS procurement
- Provide a forum for open exchange of information relative to TPS requirements
- Incorporate lessons learned

This effort resulted in the development of the Red Team package. This package was used as the starting point for all CASS FoT OTPS procurements within the Navy, primarily for Intermediate Level (I-Level) sites. Since its introduction, the Red Team package has been scrutinized by Navy organizations and private industry.

In 2005, the Red Team package went under an overhaul in an effort to standardize the procurement package for multi-service acquisitions. This was accomplished by developing a standard TPS Performance Specification (MIL-PRF-32070). This specification superseded MIL-STD-2077B and became the approved specification for use by all Department of Defense (DoD) agencies. Since each service has unique requirements, the Navy created an addendum to this specification that maintained all of the Navy peculiar requirements based on the host ATE. These requirements were captured in the MIL-PRF-32070 Addendum that can be tailored for each Navy procurement as necessary.

NAVAIR Generic OTPS RFP

This overhaul of the Red Team package resulted in a new RFP package that was renamed as the NAVAIR Generic OTPS RFP (NGOR). The NGOR package is comprised of the following

elements:

Table 1. NGOR Attachments	
Attachment 1	Statement of Work
Attachment 2	MIL-PRF-32070 Addendum
Attachment 3	General Acceptance Test Procedures
Attachment 4	Technical Data Package Requirements
Attachment 5	Technical Manual Requirements
Attachment 6	Provisioning Statement of Work
Attachment 7	Addressee List
Attachment 8	Distribution Statements
Attachment 9	DD-Form 254
Attachment 10	Storage Case Drawings
Sections B-M	Contract

Used in conjunction with the MIL-PRF-32070 TPS Performance Specification, each of these sections of the NGOR can be tailored by the procuring activity Integrated Product Team (IPT) to capture unique platform requirements. This tailoring may include, but not limited to: Intermediate Level vs Depot Level requirements, offload/rehost versus direct to CASS procurements, diagnostics versus test-and-check only, and Navy versus Marine Corp applications (CASS/RT-CASS).

Any data required to be delivered in the execution of a contract must be defined by Contract Data Requirements Lists (CDRLs). The CDRL identifies the appropriate Data Item Description (DID) which articulates the data requirements and establishes the preparation instructions in terms of format and content. The NGOR package contains CDRLs encompassing engineering, logistics, and program management requirements. The NGOR package contains the following CDRLs (prior to implementation of SETR):

Table 2. NGOR CDRLs (prior to SETR)	
CDRL	Description
A001	Engineering Support Data (ESD)
A002	Test Program Set Documentation (TPSD)
A003	Computer Products (Source Code)
A004	OTPS Technical Data Package
A005	Product Tool List
A006	Request for Deviations
A007	Software Version Description
A008	Source Control Drawing Request
A009	Integrated master Schedule (IMS)
B001	Acceptance Test Report
C001	Status report
C002	Conference Agenda
C003	Conference minutes
D001	Logistics Supportability Analysis
D002	Support Equipment Recommendation Data
D003	Interim Support Items List
D004	Statement of Submission
E001	Interface Device Technical Manuals
F001	Operational Security (OPSEC) Plan

III. SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

Current policy as directed by DoDI 5000.02^[1] creates an acquisition policy environment that aims at producing greater efficiency and productivity in defense spending. This instruction calls for minimization of unique ATE, thus identifying a preference for approved DoD Automatic Test Systems (ATS) families to satisfy ATS requirements.

In SECNAVINST 5000.2E^[2], the Secretary of the Navy directed that acquisition of ATE required a waiver from ASN(RD&A) if not utilizing the ATE designated for use at intermediate, depot and factory levels of maintenance. By this instruction, the Chief of Naval Operations designated CASS FoT as the Navy and Marine Corps requirement for automatic testing via OPNAVINST 3960.16A^[3].

Fig. 1. Acquisition Policy

The Commander, Naval Air Systems Command, defined the processes, roles, and responsibilities for the acquisition and sustainment of ATE and OTPSs. This was issued as policy in NAVAIRINST 13630.5^[4]. In addition to establishing CASS as the Navy’s standard ATE, it designates PMA260 as having the responsibility to develop and maintain a generic OTPS procurement package, including OTPS acquisition and sustainment processes. This generic procurement package is the NGOR.

In an effort to adhere to Naval Air Systems Command Systems Engineering (SE) policy, per NAVAIRINST 5000.24^[10], the NGOR IPT was tasked with revising the NGOR package for compliance with NAVAIRINST 4355.19^[6] Systems Engineering Technical Review (SETR) process. The SETR instruction was developed by the NAVAIR Systems Engineering Development & Implementation Center (SEDIC) and has been adapted for use within the procurement of Test Program Sets (TPSs) used on the CASS FoT.

The ultimate purpose of the Systems Engineering process is to provide a framework allowing effective and efficient delivery of capability to satisfy a validated operational need. To fulfill that purpose, systems engineering processes are implemented in an integral and overlapping manner to support the iterative maturation of the system solution. As depicted in Figure 2 below, the systems engineering process begins with identification of a validated operation need.

Fig. 2. Systems Engineering "V" Curve

On the left side of the SE "V" model, the system progresses from a general outline of the requirements of the system into detailed specifications of the system design. The system is initially decomposed into subsystems and further into subsystem components. The decomposition of the system includes identifying broad operational requirements and conveying them into more specific and derived requirements which are allocated to the system and subsystem components.

As design and development progresses, a series of documented baselines are established that support the proceeding steps. The system/subsystem hardware and software are established at the bottom of the "V". The system/subsystem components are then integrated and verified in an iterative fashion on the right. Ultimately, the completed system is validated to ensure it meets the user's needs.

The SETR process is an integral part of systems engineering and life-cycle management of acquisition and modernization programs. SETRs are a fundamental method for assessing the health and maturity of a program at critical points in its life cycle. The SETR timing is depicted in Figure 3 below. The health of a program is assessed at major SETR milestones. Program Managers (PMs) in conjunction with IPT members will coordinate for an independent assessment of program readiness to enter into the next development phase. Insight is applied to the maturing design in the assessment of requirements traceability, product metrics, and decision rationale. SETRs bring additional independent subject matter experts (SMEs) to the development process in an effort to ensure program success. The primary objective of SETR is a well-managed and disciplined technical effort leading to a successful system/subsystem evaluation that ensures fielding of a suitable and effective operational system for the warfighter.

Systems Engineering Technical Review Timing

Fig. 3. SETR Timing

SETRs assess the total system, which in the OTPS community is composed of hardware, software, and documentation, but also includes stakeholders; fleet users, maintainers, and IPT members; as well as facilities, infrastructure, and operating environment.

By policy, the SETR requirements apply to PEO programs (ACAT I thru IV) involved with design, development, test and evaluation, acquisition, in-service support and disposal of naval aviation weapon systems and equipment. The NAVAIRINST 4355.19 also states that "... the SETRs may also be applied to Abbreviated Acquisition Programs (AAPs) and other non-ACAT programs as determined and tailored by the cognizant PEO and/or program manager."^[6] The challenge for the acquisition NGOR IPT is incorporating the SETR requirements of NAVAIRINST 4355.19 into the existing NGOR baseline.

"This instruction applies to all NAVAIR, which includes NAVAIR Headquarters, Competencies, Program Executive Officers (PEOs), Program Managers AIR (PMA), subordinate commands and field activities involved with the design, development, test and evaluation (T&E), acquisition, in-service support, and disposal of Naval aviation systems and equipment. For Joint programs with Navy as the lead service, this instruction applies, but may be amended to accommodate partner interests."^[6]

IV. PRE-ACQUISITION DOCUMENTATION

A tailored version of the Department of Defense (DoD) acquisition process is used to procure OTPSSs. Its basis is founded on risk reduction of cost, schedule, and performance of a program.

The pre-acquisition phase, (Figure 4 – Acquisition Timing), of OTPS procurement is initiated by Program Management Air (PMA) in providing information about the weapons system maintenance requirement through an Initial Capabilities Document (ICD) or equivalent request. The weapons system current and future maintenance concepts are

then researched to establish feasibility of developing support equipment. An Analysis of Alternatives (AoA) is created from the information gathered. If the AoA produces a positive return on investment (ROI), an acquisition strategy is established for the alternative that produces the best ROI. The process of planning, developing, and coordinating produces a strategy for a program commensurate with the program’s technical risks, life cycle phase, and overall objectives. An acquisition strategy review is held to officially start the procurement cycle. Several programmatic, logistical and technical documents are created to support the pre-acquisition phase. This discussion will highlight the engineering aspects.

Fig. 4. Acquisition Timing

The requirements analysis process begins at the onset of a program. Technical requirements and related analyses form the foundation for engineering design, development, and implementation. Research is performed for defining, at a high level, qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the Interconnecting Group (IG). Typical inputs to the requirements analysis process include but are not limited to: warfighter needs, objectives and operational requirements, Measures of Effectiveness (MOE), Measures of Suitability (MOS), Measures of Performance (MOP), environments, Key Performance Parameters (KPP), Key System Attributes (KSA), technology base, output requirements from prior application of SE processes, program decision requirements, suitability requirements, and project constraints. These requirements are documented in the Requirements Analysis Document (RAD) and typical reference documents are the CASS FoT Operational Requirements Document (ORD), the ICD, military specifications, stakeholder requirements, and Fleet surveys.

Further decomposition of the technical requirements are used to generate a System Performance Specification (SPS). OTPS general requirements are from MIL-PRF-32070A^[8] and US Navy specific, Attachment 2A of the legacy NGOR. Specific requirements originate from original equipment manufacturer (OEM) test requirements documents (TRD), OEM UUT specifications, OEM acceptance test procedures

(ATP), and the stakeholder. A requirements traceability verification matrix (RTVM) is part of the SPS and documents each of the specification requirements, providing bi-directional traceability as decomposition commences, with a method of verification identified to ensure all of the requirements are validated for compliance. The SPS is reviewed by various engineering discipline SMEs culminating into a Specification Review Board (SRB), approving the specification for use, becoming Attachment 2 of the Contract, and establishing the **performance** baseline .

Systems engineering activities and the technical program approach are captured in Systems Engineering Plan (SEP). The purpose of the SEP is to provide the program with a disciplined systems engineering approach that incorporates a well-documented technical foundation for the program. The SEP is a living document in which periodic updates capture the program's current status, evolving implementation of SE, and its relationship with program management. The SEP also captures all the planned Systems Engineering Technical Reviews (SETR). Technical performance measures (TPM), KPPs, and KSAs are listed and tracked in the SEP as well. All sections of the SEP are driven by Section 139b of title 10 United States Code and DoDI 5000.02 policy. The approved SEP and SPS form the technical "Bible" for a program.

NAVAIRINST 3960.2D, "Acquisition Test and Evaluation"^[9], captures the Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP). The TEMP, along with the NGOR Attachment 3 GATP contains the testing concepts, events, funding, resources, and acceptance criteria for a program. Testing is separated by a contractor led event, Developmental Test post Milestone C (DTC-1) and independent government testing, DTC-2.

V. NGOR WITH SETR APPLIED

As previously discussed, systems engineering has been a staple of CASS FoT OTPS development. The applied systems engineering principles have NOT changed in US Naval support equipment design, implementation, and sustainment. Invoking the SETR process has changed the acquisition process to improve understanding and monitoring of overall program health, design maturity, technical requirement traceability and risk reduction. SETR reviews are meant to assess program technical status, NOT to uncover new information or issues. Technical Interchange Meetings (TIM) and "Build-Up" TIMs are for technical decision making and resolution.

SETR requires a technical review board (TRB) chairperson, an impartial participant overseeing the implementation of policy set forth by DoD, SECNAV, NAVAIR and local processes. The decision regarding whether to conduct the SETR review ultimately resides with the TRB Chair. He/she approve/reject the TRB, entry criteria, checklists, and Request for Action (RFA) chits, with the assistance of the

lead systems engineer (LSE) and IPT. Requests for a TRB Chair occur at every SETR event and may be a different individual.

The products resulting from a SETR event include an independent capability assessment, technical baseline assessment, risk assessment, risk mitigation options, request for action (RFA) forms, minutes and summary report. The summary report is based on an integrated technical (e.g., logistics, engineering, T&E) assessment of the system in development.

The latest SETR process update stresses tailorability. The proceeding describes the "super-set" of SETR events for OTPS procurement. There are also associated tailored entrance criteria and an assessment checklist for each event. The events, entrance criteria, and checklists will be tailored in accordance with (IAW) the program complexity, constraints, and risks by the IPT during the pre-acquisition phase, proposal submittal, and if required, System Requirements Review Two (SRR-II). All technical amendments will be incorporated into the SEP. Technical reviews of program maturity should be conducted when the system meets the tailored review entrance criteria and assessed SETR checklists.

SRR-II is performed after contract award with the purpose of verifying the contractor understands and has properly translated requirements into technical documentation, especially the System/Subsystem Specification, built from the SPS, and establishing a **requirements** baseline. This baseline expands upon the performance baseline into OTPS direct and derived requirements.

Preliminary Design Review (PDR) is to evaluate the maturing design as documented in Hardware Configuration Items (HWCI) and Computer Software Configuration Items (CSCI) which represent the first physical definition of the system. This design is captured in the **allocated** baseline. Examples include but are not limited to: interface device configuration, test/holding fixtures, cabling, initial circuit card assembly requirements, TPS numbering, ATE asset allocation, standard code templates, functional extension programs (FEPs) requirements, etc.

The purpose of Critical Design Review (CDR) is to evaluate HWCI compliance with the performance, design, build, acceptance, and certification requirements for the initial **product** baseline as confirmed in component level definitions. This definition is captured in the Technical Data Package (TDP). Developmental three dimensional models or two dimensional drawings sufficient to manufacture pilot production units (PPU) are necessary.

A Test Readiness Review (TRR) conducts a product and process technical assessment for an Interconnecting Group in order to determine if the test objectives and procedures are complete and satisfactory. It also establishes the CSCI

initial **product** baseline for the TPS software through source code and associated S/W documentation. A completed “GO” chain with a sufficient diagnostic chain plan is required.

The System Verification Review (SVR) verifies the “as built” configuration meets all requirements established in the SPS through the close out of the Functional and Physical Configuration Audits (FCA/PCA).

The Production Readiness Review (PRR) determines if the design is ready for production and the producer has accomplished adequate production planning without incurring unacceptable risks that will breach thresholds of schedule, performance, cost, or other established criteria.

There are also non-SETR technical reviews which impart the SETR spirit but do not mandate formal SETR requests and submittals (i.e. not TRB chaired events). The Integration Readiness Planning Event (IRPE) ensures CDR RFAs have been resolved and the individual system elements are ready to enter into system integration. Government held, contractor supported Systems Engineering Readiness Reviews (SERR) are held prior to all SETR events to pre-brief the TRB Chair(s), TRB, and APMSE/Chief Engineer.

Each of the aforementioned technical reviews has entrance and exit criteria associated with the event, with the purpose of ensuring that the overall program health, risk, design maturity and technical requirement traceability have been achieved commensurate with the maturity of the program. These criteria are identified in the Statement of Work, Attachment 1 and are verified through multiple avenues including review of the applicable CDRLs, program assessment via the checklist manager, risk management boards and an independent review via a TRB chair just to name a few.

Further, each milestone event evaluates the decomposition of requirements from the requirements/performance baseline, to the functional baseline, the allocated baseline, and finally the product baseline. This decomposition is accomplished from the contract System Performance Specification (requirements/performance baseline), through the creation of the developers System/Subsystem Specification (SSS) (functional baseline). Decomposition continues via the development of the Software Design Documents (allocated baseline), and eventually to the CSCI (product baseline).

Similarly, the hardware is decomposed from the contract SPS (requirements/performance baseline), to the SSS (functional baseline) to the ESD/SSDD CDRL (allocated baseline), and finally to the HWCI (product baseline). Figure 5 below illustrates the typical OTPS specification tree.

Fig. 5. Typical OTPS Specification Tree

As there is a “super-set” of SETR events, there is also one for the CDRLs for OTPS procurement. Additional CDRLs are directly derived from the Naval Systems Engineering Guide, SETR checklist assessments, and various SMEs. Again, dependent upon program complexity, constraints, and risks, tailoring is highly suggested in type, content, and schedule for deliverables. The initial draft release of the NGOR with incorporation of SETR included the following CDRLs.

Table 3. NGOR CDRLs Per Draft SETR Release

CDRL	Description
A001	System-Subsystem Specification
A002	Test Program Set Documentation (TPSD)
A003	Computer Products (Source Code)
A004	Product Drawings/Models and Associated List (TDP)
A005	Problem Identification Report (PIR)
A006	Systems Engineering Management Plan (SEMP)
A007	Safety Assessment Report (SAR)
A008	Software Development Plan (SDP)
A009	Software Version Description (SVD)
A010	Software Requirements Specification (SRS)
A011	Software Design Description (SDD)
A012	System/Subsystem Design Description (SSDD)
A013	Developmental Test Process (DTP)
A014	System/Segment Interface Control Specification (ICS)
A015	Interface Design Description (IDD)
A016	Interface Control Document (ICD)
A017	Contractor Integrated Technical Information System Implementation Plan (CITIS-IP)
A018	Hazardous Materials Management Program (HMMP) Report
A019	Manufacturing Plan (MP)
A020	TPS Integration Logbook
A021	Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP)
B001	Acceptance Test Report
C001	Status report
C002	Conference Agenda
C003	Conference minutes
C004	Integrated Program Management Report (IPMR)
C005	Contract Work Breakdown Structure (CWBS)
D001	Logistics Supportability Analysis
D002	Support Equipment Recommendation Data
D003	Interim Support Items List
D004	Statement of Submission
D005	Instrument Calibration Procedures
D006	Calibration Measurement Requirements Summary
E001	Interface Device Technical Manuals
F001	Operational Security (OPSEC) Plan

This new SETR compliant version of NGOR was released in draft form in February 2015, posted to the PMA-260 website. Multiple programs were initiated using this draft version of SETR. As a result hosting Data Review Boards and applying lessons learned across these multiple programs, the NGOR IPT is looking at tailoring this super-set down to reduce replication of information and streamline the procurement effort. The NGOR IPT is doing this re-evaluation via consultation with SMEs and TRB chairs to ensure that the consolidation of requirements is appropriate and compliant with policy. Below is a list of the CDRLs that are being evaluated as the new SETR baseline, pending approval.

Table 4. NGOR CDRLs Revised SETR Release (Tentative)

CDRL	Description
A001	System-Subsystem Specification
A002	Test Program Set Documentation (TPSD)
A003	Computer Products (Source Code)
A004	Product Drawings/Models and Associated List (TDP)
A005	Problem Identification Report (PIR)
A006	Engineering Support Data
A007	Software Version Description (SVD)
A008	Software Design Description (SDD)
A009	Developmental Test Process (DTP)
A010	TPS Integration Logbook
B001	Acceptance Test Report
C001	Status report
C002	Conference Agenda
C003	Conference minutes
C004	Integrated Program Management Report (IPMR)
C005	Contract Work Breakdown Structure (CWBS)
D001	Logistics Supportability Analysis
D002	Support Equipment Recommendation Data
D003	Interim Support Items List
D004	Statement of Submission
D005	Instrument Calibration Procedures
D006	Calibration Measurement Requirements Summary
E001	Interface Device Technical Manuals
F001	Operational Security (OPSEC) Plan

Risks are inherent in any program. Risk management is emphasized in the SETR process. The SETR process lists an acceptable level of risk and proper mitigation plans as an exit criterion for every SETR event. Risk management boards (RMBs) are mandatory prior to technical reviews and at any time the IPT recognizes the probability of completing key milestones, events, tasks/activities, and performance parameters are affected.

Throughout an OTPS acquisition, requirements traceability is a necessity. A computer aided system engineering (CASE) tool to manage requirements is suggested for requirements management. At each design review and SETR event, system requirements incorporation into the allocated and product baselines shall be demonstrated. System requirements verification occurs during the testing phase and the process of verification is documented in the Developmental Test Process (DTP).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

System engineering has proven to be successful in the design, development, and life cycle management in OTPS procurements. The addition of the SETR process to the NGOR creates a detailed, structured framework for the OTPS acquisition and development communities to; better create, understand, and manage stakeholder requirements; reduce cost, schedule, and performance risks; and to develop a value added product for the Fleet.

The current NGOR packages are available on the PMA-260 website at <https://pma260.navy.mil>. The NGOR package incorporating SETR requirements is in DRAFT

form and is going through reviews concurrent with the NAVAIR OTPS Acquisition and Sustainment Process^[5] and will be released as a baseline upon completion of these reviews. In the interim and after formal release, the NGOR IPT will continue to incorporate updates as necessary to ensure requirements are value added, clearly defined, and lessons learned are encompassed. Further, the NGOR package will be reviewed against the newer SETR requirements of NAVAIR INST 4355.19E recently released.

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